

Teachers' Teaching Efficiency during Pandemic: A Case Study

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Abstract: The study utilized a case study to describe and gain insights from the experiences of the teachers' teaching efficiency during the pandemic within the SY 2020-2021. The study revealed that the participants felt emotional and mental distress and they have tried several strategies in order to keep their teaching efficient. They also sense the importance of equipping themselves with the recent educational tools. In order to surpass the challenges, the support of the stakeholders and the parents are the key components which are the coping mechanism of the teachers. The teachers' competence, commitment, and dedication were also equally important as they are the prime movers of the program. These qualities and positive outlook served as the tools to cope with the new normal and be an effective teacher during this pandemic.

Keywords: educational management, teachers' teaching efficiency, during pandemic, new normal education, case study, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic has affected all sectors of the society, particularly in education. The crisis has led to an education crisis for which no one was prepared. School closures worldwide have affected millions of pupils, the effects of which are yet to be known (Demuyakor, 2020). Emergency remote teaching is the temporary solution (Bozkurt, Flores, Gago; Tria, 2020). The rapid change in location forced the teachers to shift dramatically into a new digital age, a place where technology dominated every aspect of teaching. It also led us to significant and systematic changes in different ways, such as how we connect with students, how we offer online lessons, and how we evaluate students in virtual classrooms (Bech & Knudsen, 2019; Cuban, 2013; Hoem, 2009; Senge, & Smith, 2020).

Despite this, the aims and aspirations of every society can be accomplished by adequately educating its people. We need efficient teachers for such an educational scheme. It is well recognized that the teacher is the constructor of the country. The instructor must become aware of his position in the society to discharge such high responsibility. Teachers form an essential part of the contribution of human capital to education. They continue to contribute to the teaching-learning process that influences students' academic success, regardless of what happens or the world situation due to this pandemic (Banks, 2015; Light, Calkins & Co, 2009; Wanjala, 2017).

It has been stipulated that there are no permanent and predetermined solutions to problems in the education system. Teachers themselves will have to make the final choices from among the several alternatives. They are the integral part of the society. Human beings are a product of the society, where society often relies on its people for its development (Baron, 2020; Boloix, 2019; Casey, 2017; McClure; 2019).

Furthermore, this research is fundamental because the teachers make up many government employees and can be found in every corner of this world. Only when the instructor is productive in the subject material and teaching the subject, practical guidance in studies can be realized. From this point of reference, I am motivated to conduct the survey to determine and assess the teachers' teaching efficiency during the pandemic (Tan, 2002).

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The Covid- 19 pandemic has brought a lot of challenges in the new standard of education. This has significantly affected the teachers' teaching efficiency experiences. This study would like to know the experiences of these teachers as this may cause worry among the study's target beneficiaries and come up with the implication to practice, thus the need to conduct an investigation.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to describe and provide an in-depth understanding of the teacher's teaching efficiency during this new normal education at Bula District, namely Jose Divinagracia Sr. Elementary School, Bula Central Elementary School, and East Elementary School year 2020-2021.

Purpose Statement

This study aimed to know the efficiency of the teachers, teaching-learning delivery, and strategies which are the tools for monitoring efficiency in the provision of education. The researcher was interested in discovering the teachers' experiences as they raise concerns to the intended beneficiaries of the study: What are their experiences during this new normal way of teaching? How efficient are they? and what are the insights of the teachers about their unique ways of education which can be beneficial for future use and to come up with the implication to practice? It was further aimed to document the teachers' teaching efficiency during the new normal in selected three schools in Bula Districts namely: Jose Divinagracia Sr. Elementary School, Bula Central Elementary School, and East Elementary School. The information needed will be gathered using the validated survey questionnaires. The researcher considered the three identified elementary schools in General Santos City as the subjects of the study. The participants of the study were five master teachers who have a rating of very satisfactory in their Performance Commitment and Review Form rating for three consecutive years in their service. In the three selected elementary schools of Bula District Year 2020-2021.

The study was dependent on the ability of the informants and the participants to describe their experiences and to answer the given questionnaires to know their teaching efficiency during this what we called 'new normal.' Since the teachers' teaching efficiency significantly impacts the learners' performance during this pandemic, it is necessary to gain access to the informants, teachers, principals, superintendents, and learners. This may have affected the teacher's responses, for they are the study's respondents. The administration would find out the teachers' responses during the conduct of the study.

The questions were semi-structured as open-ended questions. The researcher made the interview guides based on the responses of the teachers. The interview's goal was to obtain meaningful information data. Each respondent was assured of confidentiality in their answers. The results of the investigation may not be generalized to other regions of the country. The researcher agreed that the teachers are among the most important school-based resources in determining students' future academic success. Lifetime outcomes were also found that students taught by highly efficient teachers, as defined by the student's growth percentile (SGPs) and value-added measures, were more likely to attend college, earn more and live in a higher income (Chetty, 2016; Rivkin, Hanushek, & Kain, 2005).

Research Question

This qualitative study specifically sought to answer the overarching question?

1. How do the participants describe their teaching efficiency during this pandemic?

Delimitation and Limitations

This study only sought to determine the teaching efficiency during the pandemic of Bula District's selected schools namely: Jose Divinagracia Sr. Elementary School, Bula Central Elementary School, and East Elementary School. The information needed were gathered using the validated survey questionnaires. The researcher involved only three identified elementary schools in General Santos City as the subjects of the study. Five master teachers were delighted in their Performance Commitment and Review Form rating for three consecutive years in the three selected elementary schools of Bula District Year 2020-2021. They served as the participants and subjects of the study.

Theoretical Lens

This study is anchored on the following theories and concepts: Biddle's theory (2003), Matta et al., (2016), Jing et al., (2018), and Hunter, (2015). Role theory, it explains roles by assuming that people belong to social groups and have expectations for their behavior as well as the behavior of others. Roles are a critical component of the work engagement concept. Role theory is used to educate the self-in role process, which is necessary to adhere to engagement at work (Biddles,2003). Harnessing oneself into the work role-physically, cognitively, and emotionally is achieved when the employees feel attentive, connected, integrated, and focused in their role performance (Matta et al., 2016).

Furthermore, the individual behavior depends on how their roles evolve and are defined. Functions are formed by normative expectation and are tied to identifiable social positions in organizational contexts (Jing et al., 2018). As stipulated, role theory starts with a set of normative expectations that are assumed to determine distinct positions that correlate to the roles of behavior in interactions with others (Hunter, 2015).

Teaching efficiency during the pandemic, as they accomplish their defined tasks and responsibilities in the new normal is relevant to this research. Teachers are expected to fulfill their duties despite the complexities and problems from home, school, and the broader community. Using the perspective role theory, the researcher might draw conclusions based on the essences of the described experiences of the master teachers teaching efficacy as defined by their roles, positions, and expectations. In addition, the role theory helps explain the actions displayed by the teachers as they adjust to the new normal of education.

2. PROCEDURE

The Rationale for the Qualitative Approach

The qualitative method, mainly a case study was utilized in this research. The researcher went to the site of interest to collect information, know, describe, and gain insights from the experiences of the teachers' teaching efficiency during the pandemic within the school year 2020-2021. Mainly master teachers aged 35-50 years old, rendered 15- 25 years in the service, and have a very satisfactory rating in their IPCRF ranking for three consecutive years were the subjects of the study. The researcher used techniques to collect the data, which includes interview transcript, field notes, audio recording, that can convey the actual words or actions of the people concerned in the study. A qualitative case study is an approach to analysis that makes it easier to analyze a phenomenon using various data sources within its context. This means that the problem is not explored by one lens, but by several lenses that make it possible to expose and appreciate several dimensions of the phenomenon Accordingly, the study of human interpretation of events or phenomena from actual happenings in the real world is also a case study. The participants' experiences are invoked in the study to go deeper into their minds, to define the meaning of the experience through lengthy discussions (Yazan, 2015).

The researcher used the case study methodology because it is an efficient

method to obtain a clear understanding of human experiences, penetrating their emotions, feelings, and behaviors to gain knowledge from their experiences. The investigator also obtained the data usually through in-depth interviews with individuals who have witnessed the phenomenon being investigated. Next, horizontalization was included in the data processing, and introductory statements were derived from the transcribed interviews. Finally, these preliminary statements are translated into clusters of meanings depending on how each information falls under particular psychological and psychological reports.

These transformations are connected for a general overview of both the textural description of what was observed and the structural description of the experience and how it was experienced. In addition, the researcher incorporated the experience here with their context. Finally, the report was written so that the readers could better understand the basic framework of the information.

Qualitative analysis was used in this study to eliminate assumptions to avoid possible adverse effects of beliefs that could influence the research process, thus enhancing the quality of the research study. At all times, the researcher must be careful, mindful of his/her own viewpoints and the pre-existing views on the analysis, must learn to set aside his/her own a priori awareness and ex-prior knowledge. The researcher used questions from the interview guide, which were checked by the panelist and the esteemed research validators, who are research experts (Sinkovics, Penz, Ghauri, 2008).

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Samples and Site

The primary aim of qualitative research was to collect data by involving individuals interested in or influenced by the problem under review. From this viewpoint, the appropriate participants should have the capacity to objectively analyze and express their experiences, the awareness and understanding of the subject being examined, and the desire to share their thoughts (Creswel, 2014). The participants of my study are the five master teachers, aged from 35-50 years old, teachers who rendered 15-25 years in teaching and they have a rating of very satisfactory in three consecutive years in their IPCRF. They are the teachers in the selected schools in Bula District, namely: Jose Divinagracia Sr. Elementary School, Bula Central Elementary School, and East Elementary School.

The researcher selected five master teachers through purposive sampling based on pre-selected criteria relevant to the research study. Purposive sampling is a judgmental or subjective sampling; it is a non-probability sampling technique that focuses on the investigated participants. It is based on the participants' agreement in the three selected schools in Bula District and with the approval of the supervisors and the administrations.

The researcher wanted to get only a significant number of participants for the research, with five informants for the in-depth interviews because of the situation and to avoid face-to-face encounter to come up with an excellent qualitative review. This is enough to provide credible information and relevant data and results to a sufficient number of participants. The researcher was advised to adopt 5-25 individuals who had encountered the same phenomenon for in-depth interviews (Palinkas et al; 2013).

Concerning this, the researcher pursues expertise in qualitative research by entering deeply into the heart of the experience to find the meaning of a phenomenon, and not how many individuals have been through it. Qualitative research uses interviews to find concrete mechanisms that participants use to organize their perceptions and make sense of their environment. These structures are often obscured and taken for granted by the participants from direct observation; however, qualitative interview techniques may expose such meanings (Creswel; 2015).

Access and Permission

In conducting this case study, I considered and constituted protocols to secure the ethical and social aspects of the research undertakings. The researcher secured the approval to conduct the study from the General Santos City Division Office and from the schools where the participants are employed. After which, letters of invitation to participate were sent among the identified participants of the study. When the participants consented to the request, the conduct of data collection commenced. The researcher informed the participants of the purpose of the study and asked for the participants' consent as the responses will be recorded for the analysis and interpretation, assuring that these will be held with the utmost confidentiality. The participants were informed of their role in the study and the level of their involvement. There should be no personal interest of the researcher to any qualitative personal accounts.

Data Gathering Strategies

In data gathering, when the approval was granted, and after the guide questions were carefully scrutinized to ensure the appropriateness and validity of the research instrument, the following strategies or undertakings were done and observed:

First, I prepared the necessary materials or requirements, including the venue and audio/voice recorder. Then, the venue and time were determined during the first visit with the participants. Finally, observations were done purposely to gather first information about the people and places at the research site. Second, before the interview, the participants were given a copy of the consent form for signing. It contains the study's objectives, the approaches and methodology, confidentiality, and benefits, including the contact number of the researcher. For clarifications or verifications of the purpose, the participants were given the utmost opportunity to ask. After which, with no questions or clarifications, the consent forms were retrieved. It was followed by the participant's agreement form. The said form indicates that the agreement is not just for doing research, but becoming a partner working with the participant as co-researcher. Third, the researcher transcribed the audio recordings after the interview process and utilized the member checking as a method of validation, whereby the participants read and affirmed the contents of the interview transcripts and affixed their signature on them. Such a validation process signaled the trustworthiness of the data. Lastly, as part of the case study data gathering procedure, multiple data sources were utilized, such as interviews, documents, and observations.

Data Analysis Procedure

An in-depth interview was conducted with the five master teachers aged from 35-50 years old; these master teachers rendered 15-25 years in teaching. They are those who have a rating of very satisfactory in three consecutive years in their IPCRF. After the researcher prepared the interview guide questions, these questions were validated by the respected validators according to their expertise. Analysis of the data in this research study involved summarizing the data, collecting and presenting the outcomes to highlight the essential aspects. Data were analyzed using the data reduction method, data display, conclusion drawing, and verification. In the data analysis, three steps were employed patterned after the study (Gempes et al.; 2015). This research used data reduction, which is the abstraction of transcription data, the elimination of non-important data, and the transformation into accessible information easily understood. In explaining the cases of the master teachers teaching efficiency during the pandemic at Bula District, this case study evaluated the data by thematic analysis. In research, thematic analysis is a common form of qualitative data analysis. The thematic analysis emphasized examining and recording patterns or emergent themes within the data. The thematic analysis should commence with repeated data readings. The next step involves data coding, which consists of defining and labeling (coding) quotations in the text related to the study objective. The third stage consists of the theme recognition process. Emerging themes are trends across data sets that are important for a phenomenon's definition and are related to specific research questions (Miles, Huberman, Saldana, 2014). This report distinctively adopted this research analysis approach. First, all the participants' answers were transcribed by the researcher, and relevant statements were established. Second, the analyzed meaningful reports can generate concepts and ideas to help formulate meanings from the participants. Third, the composed purposes were subjected to another research process and explicitly assigned to various ideas. Fourth, to create the clustering of essential themes, the researcher scrutinized all relevant pictures. Fifth, the researcher looked at the cluster for potential emerging themes. Sixth, by category, the themes were then grouped and clustered. Finally, to illustrate all the patterns from the participants' comments, the researcher created a convergence of statements.

Inclusion Criterion

The research participants in this study were the five master teachers, aged from 35-50 years old, who rendered 15-25 years in teaching. They are those who have a rating of very satisfactory in three consecutive years in their IPCRF. They are from the selected schools in Bula District namely: Jose Divina-gracia Sr. Elementary School, Bula Central Elementary School, and East Elementary School.

3. FINDINGS

Description of Participants

The participants of this study are the top-performing master teachers. They have rendered 15-25 years in the service and have very satisfactory rating performance for three consecutive years in their IPCRF school year 2020- 2021. Participant 1- under its code name, "white lily." I, 45 years of age and a master teacher in Jose Divinagracia Sr. Elementary School. She served as a public-school teacher for 20 years. She graduated with her master's degree at Quezon Academy, a strategic and resourceful master teacher. Participant 2- Code name "red tulips." I, 50 years of age and a master teacher at Bula Central Elementary School. She served in her teaching profession for 25 years. She finished her doctoral units at Notre Dame Graduate School University, a teacher with compassion and a supportive motherly master teacher. Participants 3- Code name "yellowbelly." I, 48 years of age and a master teacher at Dadiangas East Elementary School. She graduated with her master's degree at Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges Graduate school. A flexible and optimistic master teacher, as I may describe her. Participants 4 - Code name "golden duranta". 46 years old master teacher at East Elementary School. Served teaching in the public school for 24 years now. She graduated with her master's degree at Notre Dame Graduate School. A workaholic and selfless teacher as I may look and describe her. Participants 5- Code name "dancing lady." 41 years old master teacher at Jose Divinagracia Sr. Elementary School. She graduated with her master's degree at Holy Trinity Graduate School. A patient and understanding teacher as she describes herself. She is loving, and she shows kindness towards her pupils.

Analysis of Themes

Teaching Adjustments

The first cluster theme under the Teaching Adjustments is flexibility. It has emergent themes based on the responses categorized as the learning delivery modalities and home visitation.

Flexibility

Being able to use a variety of teaching techniques and strategies are referred to as flexibility. This talent is also helpful in the classroom when the instructor needs to change her plans for various reasons, especially in this new regular school setting. Participant 1 knew that teaching was genuinely challenging at the time of the pandemic. Much as she wants to implement online distance learning, there are limitations in terms of gadgets. Aside from the modules, she incorporated the use of mobile phones. The need for social distancing, this virtual learning platform has significantly reshaped and innovated how they teach and engage with their medical trainee's. In addition, it has allowed them to continue to foster a sense of community that they hope can attenuate trainee's burnout and promote wellness in time when isolation has become a part of everyday life. Thus, program-specific virtual learning platforms have the potential to play an essential and valuable role in learning (Chick and Hale; 2020). In an interview with participant 1, when asked about what strategies she used to teach new normal, she stipulated that learning delivery is one of the teaching adjustments in distance learning. The need for different teaching strategies is essential in this distance learning. Hence, she must adjust that some of her pupils have no internet connections or gadgets to search about the lesson online. Therefore, the need for reinforcement from the teacher is essential.

Home Visitation

Another emergent theme under the cluster themes of flexibility is home visitation. Again, it's a type of service delivery model that can be used to deliver a variety of interventions tailored to the needs of the students. Creating ties and connections with the children and parents they work with is one of the most important things teachers do. Individual relations between instructors and parents and children impact daily interactions with them and can serve as a basis if difficult situations emerge. Home visits (for Infant and Toddler Early Childhood and possibly Lower Elementary levels) are an excellent opportunity for teachers to form an initial bond with a child and his family (Patton; 2015). The teacher should be prepared to answer any questions or concerns that parents may have about Montessori, the school's particular program, or the logistics of starting school. Allowing parents time to talk about their children (something every parent enjoys) and being receptive to their questions and concerns, the teacher establishes a crucial relationship with parents (A Publication of Montessori Society; Patton, 2015). Participant 2 believes that home visitation is needed during this new normal way of educating the learners. To check the progress of her learners, the master teacher shows flexibility by home visitation to follow-up and help her the learners in their lesson. The teacher speaks about one of her teaching adjustments in the new normal: double time and effort in doing her work. Aside from the fact that she has modules to sort, the burden also is that some pupils have no access to social media. It's hazardous to have a home visit for the pupils, but she still does it to update the pupils and follow-up the outcome out of the lesson plan that she made for the parents' guide. She needs to do these because some parents have no gadgets. She just followed safety protocols for her safety. Although, there is a low case in Mindanao of the COVID-19; schools and institution they must still follow the protocol of the given by the DepEd it is for the safety of the student but also for the safety of parents and teachers as well (Fontanos, Gonzales, Lucasan & Ocampo, 2020).

Resourcefulness

When faced with Teaching Adjustments, teachers' resourcefulness can be relied on. This is the cluster theme that surfaced with two emergent themes: Contextualization and Innovation. The second clustered theme is resourcefulness. As the Covid-19 strikes our nation, the school curriculum and school setting are affected. Teachers must be resourceful and encourage their pupils and co-teachers to stay positive and work for the quality education amidst our situations. Teachers are said to be innovative if they can use all of their necessary skills, competencies, and abilities to maximize learning outcomes and achievements, with the results visible in the learner's behavior and performance. In other words, a teacher's ingenuity is judged by his output. The inventiveness of the teacher has a significant impact on the learning outcomes. Students differ in talents, so prior knowledge, and home backgrounds, highly resourceful teachers are thought to be better able to employ the most appropriate ways and materials to teach them. Differences in teacher effectiveness are, in fact, by-products of their resourcefulness and a key determinant of differences in students' learning (Nwankwo & Chiappa, 2013).

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Contextualization

Since teachers could not continue the usual face-to-face classes, their resourcefulness is needed to implement the learning continuity plan. They ensure that a strategy suits the learning needs. Their responses lead to the emergent theme, contextualization, which is most exemplified by participants 3. Participant 3 said that she constantly monitors the situation of her learners, she tried different teaching distance learning approaches assess if they are with her learners. Analyzed research on student progress monitoring was considered only experimental, controlled studies. These researchers concluded that teachers use systematic progress monitoring to track their students' progress in reading, mathematics, or spelling. As a result, they can better identify students in need of additional or different forms of instruction. As a result, the design is more vital instructional programs, and their students achieve better (Fuchs and Fuchs ,2002).

Innovation

Another emergent theme is innovation. While the teacher knows that resources are limited, they innovated and made use of what is available to assess the learners' needs and hone those learners using their more recent learning tools. For example, participant 4 shared that she tells her learners to record their activities for easy monitoring and feedback. There is research that assists teachers in using the student data to continually review the efficacy of their teaching by determining whether the students are benefiting correctly from the core instructional program and if teachers are making informed instructional decisions. If they establish and measure student academic goals, give a tool for understanding how students are progressing toward stated goals, and identify students at risk for academic behavior difficulties. Present accountability proof to stakeholders can all be done with progress monitoring (Shapiro, Fiebrink, Norvig, 2018).

Creativity

Another emergent theme is creativity in today's Covid -19. Teaching normal education is quite challenging, but participant 5 inspires herself by being creative with her pupils. She embraces creativity while juggling academic requirements. In addition, participant 5 educates her learners by providing additional inputs to enhance and help her pupils. Table 1 shows that the central theme is describing the teacher's adjustment during the Covid- 19 pandemic. The researcher found out the main article, which is teaching adjustment, and under that central theme, it has 2 cluster themes. Flexibility came out and resourcefulness. Out of that cluster, emergent themes were categorized as learning delivery: Home visitation, and contextualization. These themes came out as what the participants responded about their teaching experiences during Covid- 19 pandemic. Moreover, literature proves that lack of IT infrastructure is a significant issue in remote learning. In addition, in nations such as Pakistan, education availability was already a considerable concern (Rafiq et al., 2020). According to the report, over 50 million children in Pakistan are at risk due to COVID-19. Because of the inadequate Internet access, students are unable to undertake remote learning (Malik, Nawaz, Mehmood, 2020). Based on the preceding debate, it can be concluded that both students and teachers are experiencing difficulties. The epidemic harms teachers, parents, and students. However, because of our unique circumstances, we can achieve a specific teaching performance and learning quality for our students. Teachers are required to develop new efforts that aid in the resolution of the crisis. Teachers actively interact with one another on a local level to improve the quality of instruction provided to students through online teaching methods. As instructors, parents, and children have similar experiences, there is unparalleled potential for collaboration, creative solutions, and openness to learn from others and try new techniques (Doucet et al., 2020). Because all students' assignments and exams are completed at home, educators have difficulty determining the authenticity of the work and the actual learning. Moreover, many parents guide and support their children during their learning process, and the extent and degree of support vary greatly.

Challenges

The following central theme of this case study is the challenges. When asked about their experiences in teaching this pandemic, the cluster themes self-sacrifice and emotional and mental effect came out. The pandemic had huge disruptive effects on everyday life, complex as it already was in many countries. The impact of shuttered schools and children kept at home with little or no access to learning has been catastrophic for schools, students, and parents. According to experts, a full year of education might be lost, implying that an entire cohort of pupils could be chronically behind in their studies. The crisis and its aftermath have exposed flaws in educational systems while also reforming school education into a more resilient and robust paradigm. Unfortunately, this isn't the first epidemic to hit the countries and schools, and it won't be the last. Climate change, technological shocks, and globalization have all increased the likelihood of such disasters.

Self-sacrifice

The first cluster theme that surfaced out from the responses of the participants is self-sacrificed. Being new to learning in the new normal, both the learners and teachers have faced difficulties. Nobody has come prepared for this pandemic, and education has suffered a lot. Participant 1 shared that she has no choice, but to use his/her resources just to ensure learning. The sentiment of participant 5 aside from the lack of bond papers and ink to use for printing, if not, the materials are also delayed in delivery. According to the Bureau of Labor Statistics, between 2015 and 2025, almost 150,000 new teaching jobs will be generated. Base on the National Commission on Teaching and America's Future, 20% of all new teachers quit in the field within the first three years. Being a teacher is always challenging. New instructors are confronted with unique challenges and demands that can be overwhelming in their first few years. Rather than trying to do and learn everything all at once, rookie instructors must remember to be patient while also utilizing the resources and relying on their teaching community (Groshen,2015).

Financial and Material Resources

Another emergent theme is financial resources. In this new normal of education, there is no doubt that the teachers have difficulty facilitating learners in rote learning and in reaching out with the learners and providing materials for them. Teachers have financial problems sustaining the printed materials. Financial and material resources are another emergent theme. They have a significant impact on the performance of the teacher. Teachers invest their own money to contact their learners. The teacher finds ways to support and provide quality education by investing their own money, like their load to reach their learners and buy bond papers and ink for the instructional materials for their pupils' needs. As mentioned by participant 1, because of the large number of modules and SLMS to be printed, the shortage of printers is the primary concern. They have only five printers in the school, and thousands of instructional materials will be produced. The teachers struggle in doing this. Aside from the insufficient resources, the agony, and the tiring jobs made their day stressful. In the face of insufficient school financing, out-of-pocket expenditure continues to be necessary, according to a new poll of K-12 teachers across the United States. The sixth annual teacher shopping report released today by Sheer ID and Agile Education Marketing indicates that during the 2018-19 school year, 99 percent of teachers spent personal dollars on school-related items such as science kits and art supplies, as well as snacks for the kids. According to the poll, teachers feel obligated to guarantee that their pupils have a positive learning experience at any cost (Powell, & Patrick, 2006).

Emotional and Mental Effect

The second cluster theme is the emotional and mental effects. They know that continuing education in the new normal is challenging. Teachers were emotionally battered. They became prone to stress leaving some of them restless and tired.

The pandemic has impacted students' mental health, as well as teachers, they have been under a lot of stress since the beginning of the crisis. For example, according to recent studies, teachers experienced stress during lockdown due to the need to adjust (in record time) to conduct online lectures (Besser et al., 2020). In addition, due to the increased effort caused by home teaching, this stress is frequently accompanied by worry, depression, and sleep disturbance symptoms (Cachón-Zagalaz et al., 2020).

Temper and Conscientiousness

The first emergent theme is temper and conscientiousness. Teachers have faced challenges in the new normal, and somehow tried their patience. Participant 3 was ambivalent because she could no longer assure students' learning. She knew that education could not be guaranteed even if she prepared everything, the instructional materials, and the teaching aid. She also mentioned that non-face-to-face classes tested her efficiency in teaching. Participant 3 speaks about the most challenging time of being a teacher during the new normal education. The difficulty in facilitating her learners was one of her concerns. As stipulated, the teachers' health may suffer due to stress, which could lead to more sick days, absenteeism, and poor work performance. Therefore, it is critical, according to the research, to protect teachers' emotional health. Teacher-student relationships also stress the students (Dela Fuente & Peterson, 2014).

Anxiety and Stress

The second emergent theme in emotional and mental effects is anxiety and stress. All of the participants shared that their teaching vocation affected their daily routine. For example, participant 4 said that she had difficulty sleeping as she kept on worrying about her learners. She also felt paranoid about her safety in school every time she went according to the research conducted, there are two probable protective factors for teachers' mental well-being. First, instructors who have better emotion management skills reduced burnout and have higher job satisfaction. These abilities include reliably perceiving emotions, comprehending their causes and consequences, appropriately labeling them, expressing them comfortably, and effectively managing them (Cipriano & Huit, 2020).

Depression

The third emergent theme is depression. The Covid -19 pandemic affects the mental health of teachers. Teachers are dealing with new measures, insecurity, and a lack of clear guidelines about coping with their feelings.

Participant 5 felt depressed about the specific situation. Her overlapping of work and the agony that she felt about her safety in Covid- 19 made her depressed. The master teacher has a poor appetite because of the particular situation. Research revealed that the teachers are exposed to various sources of stress, and one of these is the workloads. To cope with these challenges, teachers discuss their problems with their family members, peers and take training and programs for personal development and resilience (Sandilos, Scheffner Hammer, Lopez, Blair, 2018). In addition, Pakistani universities have Internet access and equipment on their campuses. On the other hand, universities find it difficult to give these services to students at their homes. Not only is the Internet access difficult, but the broadband service availability is also problematic, according to a recent survey. Students in Pakistan cannot afford these amenities (Malik, Zhu, Nawas, Mehmood, 2020). Table 2 shows that the central theme is the challenges of the teachers in teaching during the Covid-19 pandemic. First, the researcher found out the main article, which is teachers' teaching challenges. Under that central theme, it has 2 cluster themes. First,

the self-sacrifice came out under the cluster theme of self-sacrifice. Second, two emergent themes came out: hard work, financial and material resources. Another second cluster theme is Emotional and Mental Effects. Out of that cluster, two emergent themes emerged: the temper and conscientiousness, anxiety, stress, and depression. These themes came out as what the participants responded about the challenges of teaching in the new normal setting. This set of difficulties aided the research of Fageeh (2020). However, his previous research study shows that both teachers and students are open to change. The transformation of traditional face-to-face learning to new learning modalities is referred to as change (Fageeh et al., 2020).

Embracing the New Normal

The last central theme established from the case study is embracing the new normal. It has three cluster themes: curriculum support, stakeholders, support, and teachers' commitment and dedication.

Curriculum Support

The first cluster theme under embracing the new normal is curriculum support. It has three emergent themes: capability building, provision of instructional materials, and technological advancements.

Capability Building and Technical Support

Knowing that the teachers are at the forefront of educational services, capability building among teachers is necessary to make them equipped and ready for the new normal.

Participant 1 admitted that she is not trained to handle the new learning modalities; yet the webinars provided by the Department of Education helped them cope with the various changes. The teacher admitted that she was not hundred percent ready to teach in the new standard settings. However, through the initiatives of the Department of Education, before the classes start, they have attended several virtual webinar trainings for them to be ready in the new usual way of teaching. The said webinars help them to renew some teaching techniques in teaching their learners (Ferdig, Baumgartner, Hartshorne, Kaplan-Rakowski & Mouza, 2020). The master teacher also stipulates that she collaborates with the I.T experts to help her be equipped with the 21st facilitating skills for better teaching. Teachers have a challenging year,

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thinking about how technology could be utilized to keep students safe and engaged in school during the pandemic. Root & STEM's debut episode looks at how educators from all across the world are dealing with the pandemic, whether online or in the classroom (Wang, Zhang, Zhao, Zhang, & Jiang, 2020).

Instructional Materials

Another emergent theme is instructional materials. These are essential tools in learning every subject in the school curriculum. They allow students to interact with words, symbols, and ideas to develop their reading, listening, and thinking abilities. In this new normal setting of teaching, these instructional materials are essential. Participant 2 said that the instructional materials are needed. She searches on websites about different learning materials. The teacher emphasized the importance of preparing her instructional materials by searching the websites of the DepEd portals about ways on how to enhance and make comprehensive learning materials for her lesson. Many researchers described the instructional materials as tools that help the teacher in teaching, any natural materials, the teacher or student-made materials, and any manufactured objects that promote good teaching and learning. Such materials and tools provide opportunities for the teacher and learners to enjoy the meaningful and exciting classroom. However, it is not expected that the instructional materials should take the teacher's place in the school. Instead, they should be appropriate resources that, when effectively used, enhance students' learning (Koko, Kusakana, & Vermaak, 2015).

Technological Advancements

The second emergent theme is Technological Advancements. The new normal in education magnifies the need for education to use advanced technology. The pandemic is swiftly highlighting the importance of online education in teaching and learning. Teachers may utilize online learning as a solid instructional tool by incorporating technology into existing curricula rather than treating it purely as a crisis-management tool. As a result, students' engagement can be increased, teachers' lesson plans can be improved, and personalized learning may be facilitated through digital learning technologies in the classroom. It also assists pupils in developing critical 21st-century abilities.

Stakeholders Support

The second cluster theme is the stakeholder's support. The participants of this study affirmed that the role of parents is essential in embracing the new normal. Since all the learning occurs at home, they sense that parents have to cooperate and become facilitators of learning in the absence of face-to-face classes.

Teachers Commitment and Dedication

The last and final cluster theme for embracing the new normal is the teacher's commitment and dedication. The participants mentioned that this pandemic caused them so much stress. To ensure that learning in the new normal will succeed, teachers have to play a vital part in bringing in their commitment to support the program of the Department of Education as well as give their dedication to ensure quality services despite the challenges. Teachers find ways to get the "job done" because their workload is based on national standards of what constitutes teacher efficiency, which will later act as the basis for their performance assessment (Moran et al., 2015). In the recent study, teachers possess optimism and positivity. They took the responsibilities through proper planning and time management. Despite the challenges, they shared positive insights about their experiences on commitment and dedication, being positive, prospects for growth and development, and as a testament of faith and trust in one's ability (Into & Gempes, 2018). Table 3 shows the central theme which is the teachers' Embracing the New Normal of Education. The researcher found the main article, Embracing the New Normal, under that central theme. It has three cluster themes. The Curriculum Support came out, under the cluster theme of the curriculum support is one emergent theme, Capability Building.

Another cluster theme is Technical Support. Out of that cluster theme, two emergent themes came out: Instructional Materials and Technological Advancement. Another cluster theme in embracing the new normal is the Parents and Stakeholder Support. Finally, these cluster themes have one emergent theme, which is Guidance.

An effective stakeholder is fundamental to school improvement. Communication is one of the primary mechanisms used in stakeholder management (Davida van der Walt, 2020). Embracing the new typical setting of education is a curriculum development that requires the support of the teachers, parents, and stakeholders. Teachers help in executing the curriculum development of the school; thus, ample support of the teacher's needs is vital (Drilon, 2014).

4. DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the findings, comparisons to other existing studies, limitations of the research, implications for future research, and the qualitative research's overall significance on the teachers' teaching efficiency during the pandemic. The study sought to describe the participants' experiences of learning amidst the Covid-19 pandemic without face-to-face classes. Therefore, this study gathered necessary information during the in-depth interview among the participants. The result of the study may help the school administrators and teachers understand the plight of teachers during the implementation of the Learning Continuity Plan of the Department of Education with the use of alternative learning modalities. In addition, the findings will be the basis for the necessary intervention programs to help them have a healthy self-concept and motivate them to improve their teaching efficiency despite of the challenges. The participants shared ideas and experiences as public-school teachers who shifted from face-to-face classes to alternative teaching modalities. They felt emotional and mental distress, and they have tried several strategies to keep their teaching efficient. Most of them felt stressed and experienced difficulties in adjusting to the new normal of education. Some participants became restless because of the situation and were hot-tempered in the earliest days of the implementation, but later on, they have managed to use varying strategies to cope with the new trend. They often spend time at home because of Alternative Work Arrangements, but they are left with so many tasks to accomplish that need their time management. They also sensed the importance of equipping themselves with the recent educational tools. As a result, all of them are active in participating in the webinars. Some of them are also active in sharing their knowledge with other teachers.

On the other hand, they have devised mechanisms to follow up with their learners. Home visitation is done by almost all the participants, since there are learners who could not access using mobile communication nor the internet. Those with the gadget and with online connection are asked to record their performance tasks to reduce learners to be visited at home. Moreover, this activity takes so much of their time. Imagine a teacher with 48 students and how tiring it would be to have all of them visited. Although they face emotional distress, they still combat those feelings with positivity. They know that curriculum support from the agency is available. There may be a few lapses, but those are manageable. They also recognized that the parent's and stakeholders' support is vital in continuing education. They have seen how beneficial the school-stakeholder partnership is to surpass the challenges. Parents are the facilitators of learning at home, and thereby, a healthy relationship between the teachers and parents means quality delivery of educational services from home to school. The teacher's competence and commitment are also equally important as teachers are the prime movers of the program. While learning is being done at home, all the home learning plans, modules to be used, and modified assessments are still at the hands of the teachers.

Comparison of findings with existing studies

Teachers' need to make several teaching adjustments to cater to the varying learning situations. As mentioned, changes in the learning systems are forcing the schools to implement distance learning or online learning, e-learning, distance learning, communication education, external studies, flexible learning, and massive open online courses (Rasmitadlia, et al., 2020). The findings revealed that teachers coped with the new trends and equipped themselves with the new educational tools in teaching. Teachers found out that most students embraced online learning as a better option for education. However, they did not consider it as an alternative to the conventional approach to learning (Mohalik, 2020). Challenges were inevitable. In most schools, modular learning is an important aspect of the "new normal" of education, but as the following experiences in several households demonstrate, mothers and children face numerous challenges in this method of instruction. Parents/guardians play a key part in the implementation of modular learning, working as teachers and facilitators in leading their children through the learning materials. This modular distance learning is one of the solutions to pursue educating children despite of the pandemic (Ferdig, Baumgartner, Hartshorne, Kaplan-Rakowski & Mouza, 2020). It is notable that mainly an individual or team effort with the teachers, and parents has the key importance in the delivery of instruction during the new normal setting of education. This one-of-a-kind setting offers remarkable insight into the teachers' digital instruction professionalization (Gage & Berliner; 2014). Conversely speaking, parents, in particular have an active role in the learning process. They would assist and guide their children through the modular lessons sent to students while doing remote learning (Megamole & Sibayan, 2020). This study agrees with the finding that parents have a big part in the learning delivery of instruction in the new normal setting. It was supported that working parents now have more work, providing technical support or assistance with their schoolwork. It is hard adjusting everything from meetings to online classes (Adams & Todd, 2020). It was evidently shown that while the world

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faced the threat of the Covid 19 for more than a year, embracing the new normal way of learning has taken place. The teachers are left with no choice, but to ensure that they can combat whatever is ahead (Aslan and Chang, 2015). The Covid-19 indeed opens the windows of opportunities even for education. This confirms that education must also be modern and readily available in whatever conditions (Baran et al., 2014).

Teaching focuses clearly on students as end-users, even though teachers have an essential role in delivering ICT in the classroom. Thus, most teachers nowadays should be digitally literate. However, it is still necessary to learn how ICT can be used effectively and meaningfully in the classroom (Ertmer and Leftwicht, 2010). On the other hand, the lack of knowledge and skills to support ICT learning is a final impeding factor since it lacks adequate training focused on teachers' teaching practice (Albugami & Ahmed, 2015; Condy, Junjera, Tiba, 2016; Hadar et al., 2020). This study highlighted the pertinent role of the stakeholders, especially the parents, in making all the new strategies work. Multiple authors have also agreed that collegiality and collaboration were required at every phase in the shift to remote learning and teaching, requiring fine-tuned multiplexing (Graham, Williams, Isles, Buadromo, Toatu, Druce, & Williamson, 2021).

Implication for Practice

The researcher believes that teaching during this time of Covid-19 is not easy. Therefore, teachers' teaching efficiency during this time of pandemic is affected. The researcher perceives that teaching adjustment and being resourceful is one way that the teachers can cope with the situation—these adjustments category is being flexible in their field of teaching. When asked about their teaching experiences during the pandemic, the researcher realized the difficulties teachers faced. The psychological and emotional impact became apparent. It is well understood that continuing education in the modern normal is challenging. Teachers were emotionally battered. They became prone to stress and leaving some of them restless. Anxiety, Stress, Temper and Conscientiousness came out, and the teacher's way to face and embrace the situation is self-sacrifice. Being new to learning in the new normal, both learners and teachers have difficulties. Nobody has come prepared for this pandemic, and education has suffered a lot, and the only way they opted to is to sacrifice themselves. However, the coping mechanism of the teachers is embracing the new normal in which they find strength through capability building and technical support as well as the support from the stakeholders. The researcher saw the commitment and dedication of the teachers. Although the pandemic caused them so much stress, the teachers ensure that learning in the new normal succeed. Teachers have to play their vital part in bringing their commitment to support the program of the Department of Education as well as give their dedication to ensure quality services despite the challenges. From the stories and experiences of these teachers, the researcher gained insights that a positive attitude, determination, and strong commitment and dedication are vital. These characteristics and outlook in life made these teachers efficient in their work of expertise. In addition, appreciation from the school principal and the financial support from the local government, potential stakeholders, and their colleagues play an essential role in being more efficient and effective teachers. Thus, this positive outlook of the teachers plays an essential aspect in promoting quality and efficient teaching regardless of the Covid-19 pandemic.

Limitations

The participants of the study are five (5) Master Teachers from Bula Central Elementary School, General Santos City, 2020-2021. This is based on the concept of Creswell (2015). The participants involved in a qualitative study are from 5 to 25. Moreover, this study is only limited to teachers' perspectives on their teaching efficiency during the pandemic.

Implications for Future research

The results of the study were taken from the experiences of the Master Teachers on their teaching efficiency during the pandemic. Hence, another survey of the same kind may be conducted in other cities or divisions to validate the results of this study. Moreover, further research may be done to re-interview some participants to validate their feelings, views, and perceptions on their teaching efficiency during the pandemic. Other research may also be conducted from parents' perspective with diverse information to better understand the teaching efficiency of the teachers or the new trends of education during the pandemic.

Overall Significant of the Study

This crisis brought by the pandemic has shown that maintaining quality education is not only about technology or connectivity, it is the spirit of being optimistic, flexible, and resourceful. Teachers must maintain solid and good working relations with their students and deliver lessons to facilitate learning despite this challenging time. Thus, ensuring high-quality and efficient teaching and the support of the education system to provide teachers in technological and pedagogical aspects to cope in the new situation. To remain resilient as we all adapt to the new normal is predicated on providing the teachers what they need. The ability to embrace the new standard of education, to persevere and be dedicated to their work are what teachers are expected. Effective teaching depends on several characteristics, such as being optimistic, flexible, and resourceful. These are the qualities of being an efficient and effective teacher during this challenging time of Covid- 19 pandemic. In addition, the teachers embrace the new normal and accept the challenges despite the anxiety and mental health issues brought by the pandemic. Thus, the attitude of the teachers, as well as the support from the principal, colleagues, stakeholders, and good working relation with the parents are very much pivotal in facing the new normal trend of education.

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